

Curriculum to Harmonize the Hospitality Competencies from the K-12 to the BS-HRM Program

Dr. Lilibeth C. Ygonia & Mr. Edison Tejas

University of Cebu Main Campus, Cebu City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study explored the competencies of BS-HRM graduates and examined the alignment of the curriculum with the evolving needs of the hospitality industry in Cebu City. Utilizing a descriptive research design, data were gathered from hotel representatives and HRM graduates through a structured questionnaire. Results showed that the hospitality establishments in Cebu are mostly economy and resort-type hotels with varying accreditation and years of operation. Graduates were generally found to be highly competent, particularly in areas such as customer service, communication, leadership, and food safety. The transition from the K–12 program to the BS-HRM curriculum was positively perceived, although there remains a need to strengthen hands-on experiences and industry immersion. The validation of graduate competencies was strongly supported through various assessment methods such as practical tests, performance evaluations, and structured onboarding programs. Graduates also provided favorable feedback regarding the current curriculum, especially in relation to soft skills development, industry collaboration, and sustainability-focused education. The study concludes that HRM graduates are well-prepared for the demands of the industry, but there is a continuous need for academic institutions to collaborate with industry partners to ensure the curriculum remains relevant and responsive. Enhancing practical training, integrating emerging trends, and regularly reviewing the curriculum are recommended to uphold the quality and competitiveness of hospitality education.

Keywords: HRM Graduate Competencies, Hospitality Curriculum Development, Industry Relevance in Education

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

The K to 12 Program was implemented to reform the Philippine education system by extending basic education to 12 years, incorporating two additional years of Senior High School (SHS). This initiative aims to equip students with essential skills necessary for employment, further education, and entrepreneurship. Through the implementation of Republic Act No. 10533, known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the program emphasizes the development of lifelong learners who are prepared to engage in productive work, coexist harmoniously within society, and demonstrate critical and creative thinking.

Despite these reforms, challenges remain in the transition from basic education to higher education, particularly within the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BS-HRM) program. A significant issue is the persistent mismatch between the competencies of HRM graduates and the expectations of employers in the hospitality industry. This disconnect has contributed to increasing rates of unemployment and underemployment among graduates, revealing a gap between the curriculum's offerings and the actual demands of the industry. Employers increasingly seek graduates who are not only work-ready but also possess a combination of job-specific skills and higher-level attributes essential for success in the fast-evolving hospitality sector.

In response to these challenges, this study aims to investigate the employability potentials and professional traits of HRM graduates as perceived by hotel employers. By identifying the skills and attributes that are valued in the hospitality industry, the research seeks to provide valuable insights for aligning the HRM curriculum with industry needs. Ultimately, this alignment can enhance the employability of graduates, ensuring they possess the necessary competencies to thrive in a competitive job market.

Background of the Study

The hospitality industry is a dynamic and rapidly evolving field that requires professionals to possess a diverse set of competencies. In response to the growing demand for skilled workers in the hospitality sector, the Philippine government has introduced reforms to strengthen the education system. One of the most significant reforms is the K-12 program, implemented through Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. This act aims to improve the Philippine Basic Education System by extending the years of formal education and aligning it with international standards, thus preparing students for higher education, employment, and entrepreneurship.

The K-12 program is structured to encompass one year of kindergarten, six years of elementary education, and six years of secondary education, which includes four years of junior high school and two years of senior high school. According to Arnett, T. (2022), the development of employability skills plays a critical role in ensuring students are prepared for the workforce. The K-12 curriculum is designed to be learner-centered and

responsive to the needs of the students, as well as relevant to global demands. The inclusion of early childhood education, particularly Universal Kindergarten, has been shown to improve completion rates, with research suggesting that children who undergo a standards-based kindergarten program are better prepared for primary education. Moreover, the program includes Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), (Tubao et al., 2023) enhances students' ability to engage with their learning by using a language they are familiar with, building foundational skills in Filipino and English.

The Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM) program serves as a key pathway for students aspiring to work in the hospitality industry. However, despite the reforms brought about by the K-12 program, there are concerns regarding the alignment between the competencies taught in the K-12 system and those required in the BSHRM program. According to Liu, Y. (2025), the hospitality industry is ever-changing, and hotel managers must be adaptable to meet new challenges, which necessitates that HRM graduates possess not only technical skills but also leadership qualities and the ability to adapt to industry shifts. However, many employers in the hospitality sector report a mismatch between the skills of HRM graduates and the expectations of the industry, leading to issues of unemployment and underemployment.

This issue is compounded by the rapid evolution of the hospitality industry, where technological advancements and global competition require graduates to have a well-rounded set of competencies. Baird & Parayitam (2019) observed that employers often question the success of educational programs in developing these critical employability skills. Mau, T. A. (2019) emphasized that employers prefer to hire individuals who possess leadership skills and the ability to take rational initiatives. Additionally, Nägele & Stalder (2017) have described employability skills as essential "core skills" or "transferable skills" that go beyond technical knowledge and are key to achieving success in the workplace.

In light of these concerns, there is a pressing need to harmonize the competencies taught in the K-12 program with those required in the BSHRM curriculum. By identifying gaps and aligning the curriculum with industry standards, educational institutions can better prepare students for successful careers in the hospitality sector. This study aims to examine the competencies required by the hospitality industry and propose a re-engineered BSHRM curriculum that aligns with these demands.

Furthermore, the study validated the required competencies through direct engagement with industry stakeholders, such as hotel employers and HR managers, to ensure the proposed curriculum reflects real-world needs. By incorporating insights from the industry, the re-engineered curriculum aimed to enhance graduates' employability by equipping them with the skills necessary to succeed in the hospitality industry.

Research Locale

This research was conducted in thirty (30) privately owned or corporate hotels in Cebu City. To maintain confidentiality and avoid bias in data interpretation, the hotels were assigned letter codes (Hotels A, B, C... H). Only the researcher was able to identify

the actual names of the hotels to preserve the confidentiality of the information collected and ensure the accuracy of the statistical analysis. A detailed description of each hotel was considered too extensive; therefore, only the variables relevant to their profiles were discussed in the next chapter. (Please refer to the Appendix for the map of Cebu City.)

Conceptual Framework

This research study was premised on the concept that there was demand in the market for Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BSHRM) graduates ; however, the skills and competencies produced by educational institutions were deemed inadequate. Therefore, gathering employers' opinions regarding these needs was considered essential to forecast employment requirements and address the identified gaps. In view of this, an investigation on what potentials or attributes employers look for in their employees and the degree of relevance of these attributes to the graduates' employability, would establish a profile along such aspects as interactive and interpersonal skills, competency/technical and business skills and personal qualities and value orientation. The profile would enable authorities in the field to inclusion of these attributes in the school program. Through interview and dialogue supported by a survey questionnaire, the data were gathered and then subjected to analysis and interpretation. The findings of the study determined the respondents' needs, which provided a basis for integrating the results into a re-engineered curriculum. This was aligned with industry requirements and was expected to result in enhanced employability of graduates.

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study.

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the curriculum to harmonize hospitality competences from the K-12 to the Bachelor of Science in Hotel, Restaurant Management.

1. What is the profile of the selected hotels in terms of:
 - 1.1 classification;
 - 1.2 accreditation;
 - 1.3 years of operation; and
 - 1.4 number of employees?
2. How do these competencies find their way from K-12 to BSHRM program?
3. How to validate competencies through industry?
4. What re-engineered curriculum can be proposed in the BSHRM program?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant difference in the perceptions of the employer-respondents on the degree of relevance of HM graduates attributes for employability.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study focused on determining the employability potentials or attributes that hotel employers sought in their employees and the relevance of these attributes to the employability of student graduates. In this context, the study limited its respondents to General Managers, HR Directors, and Department Heads of the Food & Beverage and Housekeeping divisions of various hotels in Cebu City.

The required no. of hotels conducted as requested by the Panel Committee is twenty (20). As formal coordination with Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), no records were found. Thus, the Registrar Office of the University of Cebu (UC) could provide the needed records of the HRM graduates for the last three years from 2012-2014.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The review of related literature involves the systematic identification, location, and analysis of articles, documents and studies related to the research problem.

Related Literature

The study deals with skills, competencies, qualities or attributes required of employees in the performance of their job.

(Wang et al., 2016), describe the strategic value of employee skills and knowledge, as a human capital or more broadly intellectual capital. Employee skills, knowledge and abilities he says, are among the distinctive and renewable resources upon which company can draw success.

On the other hand, (Talaat et al., 2021) in his article report the skills and competencies that are at the core of job performance. He mentioned among others, personal qualities and interpersonal skills.

Personal qualities include displaying responsibility, self-esteem, integrity and honesty and self management. Interpersonal skills include abilities to participate as a member of a team, exercise leadership, serve clients or customers, negotiate and work with diverse people.

Talaat, et al (2002) that success or failure in a job often hinges on how well one gets along with supervisors and peers. Interpersonal relationships contribute to success at work and increase one's sense of satisfaction.

Interpersonal skills are one of a number of broadly similar terms that are sometimes used interchangeably. Other such terms include interactive skills, face to face skills and social competence (Little et al., 2017).

The term competency is described here through two broad areas; technical skills and business skills.

According to (Cherkashyn et al., 2024) technical I skills are the ability to use the tools, procedure and techniques of a specialized field. (García-Pérez et al., 2021) posits, similarly that technical skills include the ability to apply the specialized procedures, techniques, and knowledge required to get the job done.

People will always need basic technical skills, the skills needed to perform the job in order to stay employed and to advance in their job. In addition to technical skills, an employee will have

an advantage if being skillful in the business areas of finance and accounting, computers marketing, outsourcing. Finance and accounting skills are needed to understand the basic unit of all business money. Anyone combining one files with finance and accounting will be ahead of those just a single filed

Related Studies

This study was supported by similar studies which gave more insights on the importance of curriculum re-engineering as to enhance employability of college/university graduates. The following studies were credibly interesting.

(Pigden & Moore, 2019).The Concept of Employability from the Employment Research Institute, Napier University, Edinburgh, Scotland, UK has disclosed the employability of graduates, plays a crucial role in informing labour market policy in the UK, the EU and beyond. This paper analyses current and previous applications of the term and discusses its value as an exploratory concept and a framework for policy analysis. It then traces the development of the concept, discusses its role in current labour market and training strategies (with particular references the UK) and seeks to identify an approach to defining employability that can better inform labour market policy, by transcending explanations of employment and unemployment that focus solely on their supply-side or demand-side factors. Although the literature offers a range of definitions of "employability", many policy-makers have recently used the term as shorthand for the individual's employability skills and attributes'. It is argued that this 'narrow' usage can lead to a 'hollowing out' of the concept of employability built around individual factors, personal circumstances and external factors, which acknowledges the importance of both supply-and demand-side factors.

(Soratana et al., 2021). A Knowledge Supply Chain: Reengineering e-Tourism Curriculum Design, found out that the evolution from an information-based economy to a knowledge-based society requires higher education to produce intellectual outputs to match market and society needs by adjusting its educational process and praxis. Curriculum, as a core factor in refining this process, Is therefore a key part of the transformation. And has been applied to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of higher education, but still cannot fill the gap between higher education and society needs.

(David et al., 2024) study on Re-engineering the curriculum for the 21st century, disclosed that Engineering lies at the interface between science on the one hand and society on the other. It is concerned with the systematic application of scientific and mathematical principles towards practical ends for the benefit of people. Traditionally the emphasis in engineering education has been on the scientific side, with students given a thorough grounding in the basic scientific and mathematical principles underpinning their discipline. However, the constraints on engineering problem-solving today are increasingly not technical, but rather lie on the societal and human side of engineering practice. These changes require new approaches within the curriculum and by promoting active learning and encouraging students to experiment and be more creative, eLearning is one of an important number of strategies for achieving the paradigm shift that is required.

The findings of the study conducted by (Rodríguez et al., 2018) Re-engineering academic curriculum using learning outcomes, ECTS and Bologna process concepts, revealed that The ECTS process and the supporting methodologies are quite complex and complicated, requiring the involvement of all education stakeholders (faculty, students, industry, etc.). The lack of a software tool to support the available methodologies and the involved stakeholders makes the process even more complex laborious and difficult to complete. The authors are currently developing such tool.

The availability of a free software tool will therefore simplify the process and help all Universities in their effort to obtain the ECTS label and help them towards the full implementation of the Bologna Process directives. Originality/value - The paper presents the software tool ReProTool, which will provide support to the using Methodology, also taking into consideration state-of-the-art developments in the area of ECTS, Learning outcomes and the European Qualifications Framework and will thus make it possible for Universities to re-engineer their academic programs in line with ECTS, achieve ECTS certification/label and fulfill the Bologna Process directives. This will result in the improvement of academic programs offered by Universities and the creation of compatible programmers across Europe, so that students and faculty will be able to utilize the Erasmus and other mobility programmers and participate in exchange visits. Without the use of such a tool, the application of such methodologies is really a non-trivial, error-prone task. This is a very demanding task and very few Universities in Europe have managed to obtain the ECTS label.

Moreover, (Wang et al., 2016), describe the strategic value of employee skills and knowledge, as human capital or more broadly intellectual capital. Employee skills, knowledge and abilities he says, are among the distinctive and renewable resources upon which a company can draw success.

On the other hand, a very recent study conducted by Suleman (2018). titled. Graduate Employability: A Review of Conceptual and Empirical Themes, an overview of the dominant empirical and conceptual themes in the area of graduate employment and employability over the past decade. The paper considers the wider context of higher education (HE) and labour market change, and the policy thinking towards graduate employability. It draws upon various studies to highlight the different labor market perceptions, experiences and outcomes of graduates in the United Kingdom and other national contexts. It further draws upon research that has explored the ways in which students and graduates construct their employability and begin to manage the transition from HEI to work. The paper explores some of the conceptual notions that have informed understandings of graduate employability, and argues for a broader understanding of employability than that offered by policymakers.

In his article, Meeks (2017) "What Employers Want: Workplace Know-How' disclosed that the skills and competencies that are at the core of job performance. He mentioned among others, personal qualities and interpersonal skills. Personal qualities include displaying responsibility, self-esteem, integrity and honesty and self management. Interpersonal skills include abilities to participate as a member of a team, exercise leadership, serve clients or customers, negotiate and work with diverse people. Meeks (2017) that success of failure in a job often hinges on how well one gets along with supervisors and peers. Interpersonal relationships contribute to success at work and increase one's sense of satisfaction. Interpersonal skills are one of a number of broadly similar terms that are sometimes used interchangeably. Other such terms include interactive skills, face to face skills and social competence.

According to Cimatti (2016) technical skills are the ability to use the tools, procedure, techniques, and knowledge required to get the job done. The authors revealed that people will always need basic technical skills, the skills needed to perform the job in order to stay employed and to advance in their job. In addition to technical skills, an employee will have an advantage if being skillfull in the business areas of finance and accounting, computers marketing, outsourcing. Finance and accounting skills are needed to understand the basic unit of all business money. Anyone combining one field with finance and accounting will be ahead of those with just a single field

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter covers the specific research methods and techniques to be implemented in the study. It includes research design, respondents, ethical considerations, sampling technique, research instruments and validation, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

Research Design

This study adopted a quantitative research design. It utilized a descriptive-survey design, which involved the collection of data through questionnaires and interviews. These tools served as the primary means for gathering inputs used to determine and analyze the competencies required in the hospitality industry. As stated by Celis Sierra (2020), a descriptive-survey design was appropriate when the objective was to describe, observe, and document elements of a situation as they naturally occurred. Given that the purpose of this study was to explore the attributes necessary for employability, this design was suitable for studying the phenomenon in its natural context, allowing for an accurate representation of what individuals thought, felt, and did in real-world settings.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the Generals Managers, HR Directors, Food and Beverage Managers and Housekeeping Supervisors of the different hotels in Cebu City. They will be chosen using purposive sampling which involves the selection of elements known to be "typical in the field". When people who satisfy the criteria are chosen as respondents, then purposive sampling is used (Etikan et al., 2016), are detailed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents

Instrument	Respondent	f	Attributes
Interview and questionnaires	Generals Managers	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must have been employed for at least 2 years in a managerial position • Must be currently working in the hospitality industry
Interview and questionnaires	HR Directors	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must have HR management experience of at least 2 years • Must be knowledgeable about employee engagement policies and practices
Interview and questionnaires	Food and Beverage Managers	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must be responsible for daily operations in the food and beverage department • Must have at least 1 year of experience in the same position

Interview and questionnaires	Housekeeping Supervisors	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must supervise housekeeping staff and daily cleaning operations • Must have at least 1 year of experience in the hospitality sector
Interview and questionnaires	Employees	159	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must be currently employed in any department (F&B, Housekeeping, Front Desk, etc.) • Must have at least 6 months of service in the current hotel

The following are the list of notable hotels in Cebu City, Philippines, encompassing both privately owned establishments and those operated by corporations:

No.	Hotel Name	Location (Cebu City)
1	Alicia Apartelle	Banilad
2	Alpa City Suites	Hernan Cortes / F. Cabahug St.
3	Bayfront Hotel Cebu	Near SM City Cebu
4	Best Western Plus Lex Cebu	Escario Street
5	Castle Peak Hotel	Mabolo
6	Cebu Business Hotel	Colon Street
7	Cebu Grand Hotel	N. Escario Street
8	Cebu Parklane International Hotel	Near Ayala Center
9	Cebu R Hotel	Capitol Site
10	Crown Regency Hotel & Towers	Osmeña Boulevard
11	Cuarto Hotel Cebu	Capitol Site
12	Diplomat Hotel	F. Ramos Street
13	Fuente Oro Business Suites	Near Fuente Osmeña Circle
14	Golden Prince Hotel & Suites	Near Ayala Center
15	Go Hotels Cebu	Robinsons Cybergate, Fuente
16	GV Tower Hotel	Sanciangko Street / Osmeña Blvd.
17	Harolds Hotel	Gorordo Avenue
18	Hotel De Mercedes	Pelaez Street
19	Hotel Elizabeth Cebu	Near Ayala Center
20	Hotel Stella	Don Gil Garcia Street
21	Marco Polo Plaza Cebu	Nivel Hills, Lahug
22	Maxwell Hotel Cebu	Escario Street
23	MJ Hotel & Suites	Juana Osmeña Street
24	Montebello Villa Hotel	Banilad

25	Quest Hotel & Conference Center Cebu	Archbishop Reyes Ave.
26	Radisson Blu Cebu	Beside SM City Cebu
27	Sarroso International Hotel	Mabolo
28	Seda Ayala Center Cebu	Ayala Center Cebu
29	Summit Galleria Cebu	Robinsons Galleria Complex
30	Waterfront Cebu City Hotel & Casino	Lahug

Sampling and Sampling Technique

The study employed a purposive sampling technique to select respondents who are most knowledgeable and relevant to the research objectives. Specifically, the sample consisted of General Managers, HR Directors, and department heads from the Food & Beverage and Housekeeping divisions of eight privately owned hotels in Cebu City, identified confidentially as Hotels A to H. These participants were chosen because of their direct involvement in recruitment and human resource management, ensuring that the data collected accurately reflects employer perspectives on employability potentials and attributes. The purposive approach allowed the researcher to focus on key informants who could provide rich, detailed insights into the competencies required by the hospitality industry, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings.

Research Instruments and Validation

Given the quantitative design of this study, the main research instruments provides a good combination of empirical data and valuable insights. The research instruments underwent rigid face validation by the statistician. The details of the questions incorporated shown below:

Part 1	Profile of Selected Hotels	
Part 2	Assessment of HRM Graduate Competencies	20 items
	Transition from K-12 to BS-HRM Program	20 items
	Validation of Competencies	20 items
	Feedback of BS-HRM Graduates Regarding the Curriculum	20 items

Data Gathering Procedure

To be able to come up with the needed data, the following steps will be undertaken:

The study involved identifying different hotels through online research and telephone directories. Afterward, the addresses, names, and designations of the hotel managers or officers in charge were verified.

Transmittal letters addressed to the respondents were prepared and personally delivered to them for administration. This was followed by actual dialogue and interviews, during which questionnaires were administered. Once the issues had been identified, the completed surveys were gathered, analyzed, and statistically interpreted.

The questionnaire consists of multiple sections, each addressing specific objectives: Part I: collects essential background information about the hotel, such as classification, accreditation, years of operation, and employee count;

Part II: assesses how well BS-HRM graduates meet the skill and competency expectations of employers;

Part III: evaluates the effectiveness of the K-12 program in preparing students for the BS-HRM program;

Part IV: explores how employers validate the skills and competencies of new HRM graduates; and Part V gathers feedback on potential improvements for the BS-HRM curriculum.

Participants are asked to indicate their level of agreement with various statements using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," allowing for nuanced analysis of opinions.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

This study utilized a three-point Likert scale to assess the extent of usefulness as perceived by the respondents. The Likert scale provided a structured approach for evaluating responses based on a defined range of values. The statistical tools employed for data treatment were as follows:

Pearson r – Used to measure the relationship between variables and determine the strength and direction of correlation.

Percentage – Applied to express the relative frequency of responses in terms of a percentage of the total sample.

Rank – Used to rank the responses based on their order of importance or frequency.

Weighted Mean – Employed to calculate the average value of responses, giving appropriate weight to each response based on its frequency and importance.

A 4-point Likert scale was used to quantitatively assess the perceptions of hotel industry professionals regarding the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management (BS-HRM) program. It serves to evaluate the competencies of HRM graduates, measure the effectiveness of the K-12 education system in preparing students for higher education, and gather feedback on the validation methods used by employers to assess graduate skills. Additionally, the scale aids in collecting insights for curriculum development, ensuring that the BS-HRM program aligns with industry needs. By capturing the nuanced opinions of General Managers, HR Directors, Food and

Beverage Managers, and Housekeeping Supervisors, the Likert scale provides valuable data to inform curriculum improvements and enhance graduate employability in the hospitality sector.

Rank	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Individuals rated as "Very Empathetic" consistently demonstrate a deep understanding and concern for others' feelings.
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Individuals rated as "Empathetic" show a general tendency to be aware of and sensitive to the emotions of others.
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Individuals rated as "Sometimes Empathetic" occasionally recognize others' emotions but may lack consistency in their responses.
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Individuals rated as "Not Empathetic" display little to no awareness or concern for the feelings of others.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter synthesizes all research findings stated in Chapter 4 in order to formulate the conclusions and recommendations which address all the research problems mentioned in Chapter 1.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results and discussions of the research findings in Chapter 4, the summary of findings is as follows:

The study assessed the competencies of BS-HRM graduates and evaluated the curriculum's effectiveness in preparing students for the hospitality industry. Findings revealed that most participating hotels were economy-type (40.14%), accredited (69.89%), and had been operating for 1–5 years (43.37%) with 10–50 employees (36.56%). HRM graduates demonstrated strong competencies, with the overall mean of 3.44 (Strongly Agree), particularly in food safety and hygiene, communication, and leadership. The K-12 curriculum transition was rated Agree (mean = 3.17), suggesting moderate preparedness for BS-HRM programs. The validation of competencies through methods such as OJT assessments, customer feedback, and mentorship yielded a strongly agree rating (mean = 3.28), confirming that graduates' skills are continually assessed and improved in the workplace. Feedback on the BS-HRM curriculum was overwhelmingly positive, with an overall mean of 3.30 (Strongly Agree), highlighting the importance of industry collaboration, practical training, and entrepreneurial development.

Conclusions

The findings of the study confirmed that BS-HRM graduates possess strong core competencies essential for the hospitality industry. With an overall rating of Strongly

Agree, respondents highlighted the graduates' strengths in areas such as customer service, leadership, communication, and food safety. These competencies align with the expectations of employers, demonstrating that graduates are adequately prepared for roles within various hospitality settings.

While the BS-HRM graduates were deemed competent, the transition from the K–12 curriculum to the BS-HRM program revealed only a moderate level of preparedness. The average rating of Agree suggests that although the K–12 program introduces relevant skills and soft competencies, it lacks sufficient practical application needed in hospitality contexts. This implies that more experiential learning opportunities should be integrated at the basic education level.

The validation of competencies in the workplace, through practical assessments, performance reviews, and mentorship, plays a critical role in enhancing graduates' skills. The high Strongly Agree rating reflects the effectiveness of post-graduate evaluation systems used by hotels and hospitality establishments. These systems ensure that graduates continuously improve their performance and align with industry standards.

Feedback from BS-HRM graduates also suggests that the current curriculum is effective and relevant to the demands of the hospitality industry. Graduates emphasized the importance of practical training, technology integration, and exposure to various hospitality sectors. The high mean ratings across indicators suggest that a dynamic and regularly updated curriculum helps produce well-rounded professionals equipped for modern industry challenges.

Overall, the study concludes that while the current BS-HRM curriculum equips students with essential competencies, further improvements are needed in foundational education and curriculum development to keep pace with evolving industry needs. Continuous collaboration between academia and industry, along with regular curriculum evaluation, is necessary to maintain the relevance and quality of hospitality education.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

1. Strengthen industry-academe collaboration to ensure that curriculum revisions are responsive to current hospitality trends and employer expectations.
2. Enhance the K-12 curriculum by incorporating more hands-on hospitality experiences, such as simulations, field visits, and partnerships with hospitality establishments.
3. Sustain and improve competency validation efforts in the workplace, especially by using structured onboarding, mentorship programs, and regular performance reviews.
4. Promote research integration in the BS-HRM curriculum to develop graduates' critical thinking and innovation capabilities.

5. Support the continuous professional development of HRM students and graduates by offering access to certifications, workshops, and industry exposure.
6. Periodically review and update the curriculum to reflect the evolving needs of the global hospitality industry, with particular emphasis on technology, sustainability, and customer service excellence.

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